

**WORKSHOP:
"MATCHING DIVERSE FEEDSTOCKS FOR
BIOCHEMICAL RECOVERY:
IMPACT OF THEIR QUALITY"**

**VALENCIA (SPAIN)
10 - 11 JULY 2024**

**BOOK OF ABSTRACTS - WORKSHOP:
"MATCHING DIVERSE FEEDSTOCKS FOR BIOCHEMICAL
RECOVERY: IMPACT OF THEIR QUALITY"
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Welcome Message from the Action Chair

It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to the Workshop "Matching Diverse Feedstocks for Biochemical Recovery: Impact of Their Quality," held in the vibrant city of Valencia, Spain, on July 10-11, 2024. This event, organized under the auspices of the COST Action FULLRECO4US, represents a unique opportunity for experts, researchers, and practitioners from across Europe and beyond to converge, share insights, and foster collaborations in the field of sustainable resource recovery.

Our workshop aims to address the pressing global challenges of waste management and resource scarcity by exploring innovative biochemical recovery strategies from diverse feedstocks. The program includes a rich array of presentations and discussions that will delve into the quality and characteristics of various feedstocks and their impact on biochemical recovery processes. Through this, we hope to identify pathways to optimize and enhance the efficiency of these processes, contributing significantly to the circular economy.

I would like to extend my sincere gratitude to the workshop hosts, the AIMPLAS and PACKNET, and the organizing committee for their dedication and hard work in bringing this workshop to fruition. Special thanks are also due to our esteemed speakers, whose contributions will undoubtedly enrich our understanding and inspire new ideas and approaches.

I encourage all participants to engage actively the follow ups, share your valuable perspectives, and take advantage of the networking opportunities. Let us use this platform to build lasting partnerships and collaborations that will drive forward our shared goal of achieving zero waste and a more sustainable future.

Thank you for attending this workshop, and I look forward to productive discussions and successful outcomes.

Warm regards,

Mohammad Taherzadeh, Professor

COST Action Chair, FULLRECO4US (<https://fullreco4us.eu/>)

Welcome Message from the Working Group 2 Leader

It is an honour to present this Book of Abstracts as a result of the workshop held at AIMPLAS facilities in Valencia (Spain) on 10-11 July 2024 and organised in the context of the COST Action FULLRECO4US.

The theme of this event was oriented around "Matching Diverse Feedstocks for Biochemical Recovery: Impact of Their Quality" and was an excellent opportunity for the exchange of knowledge and experience of all the attendees from 16 countries.

As the leader of the Working Group 2 of this COST Action, I would like to take this opportunity to thank once again the management of the AIMPLAS technology centre for their kindness in hosting this workshop, and also to thank all the participants for their generosity in sharing with us the results of their research activity. In addition, the success of this workshop would have never been possible without the efficient collaboration with Jorge Torres (AIMPLAS) and with my colleague Mikaela Cardona (PACKNET): to them also my great thanks. Finally, a special mention to Dr Lucian Staicu, from the University of Warsaw (Poland), for his efforts in compiling and organising the contents of this book which I hope will be of interest to all members of this COST Action.

With my best wishes,

Belén García Fernández, PhD

PACKNET (Spanish Packaging Technology Platform), Managing Director

COST Action Management Committee, **FULLRECO4US** (<https://fullreco4us.eu/>)

Acknowledgments

This book of abstracts is based upon work from COST Action FULLRECO4US “Cross Border Transfer and Development of Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Towards Zero Waste” CA20133, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

Front page: Miguelete Tower (Valencia Cathedral), Valencia, Spain. Credit: ©VisitValencia

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Main keywords/Concepts

- Anaerobic digestion
- Big data
- Biogas industry
- Biomass derived catalyst materials for energy applications and water treatment
- By-products, sustainability, bioactive compounds, waste, residues, reducing, reusing, recycling
- Chemical recycling of plastics/composites
- Circular bioeconomy and effective usage of forest residues
- Critical raw materials
- Energy recovery from wastewater
- Enhanced pyrolysis & biochar applications
- Flexible & sustainable & scalable routes
- Life-cycle assessment (LCA)
- Minimal processing, food packaging, biodegradable packaging, sustainable processing, lignocellulosic fibre, packaging properties enhancement
- Minerals
- New products and markets
- Pyrolysis oil
- Reuse economy
- Respirometric assessment, mixed microbial culture, biopolymer, wastewater valorisation, PHA extraction
- Resource recovery
- Spent mushroom substrate
- Thermal hydrolysis pretreatment
- Upcycling = added-value products
- Waste heterogeneity
- Wastewater treatment
- Water
- Using char produced by different processes as support for novel catalysis or as an adsorption material

Chemical recycling of polyesters by protic ionic liquids: a factorial approach to understand and maximise the operational requirements

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Keywords: Chemical valorization; Plastic waste; Protic ionic liquid (PIL); Mechanisms; Kinetics.

Abstract

The hydrolytic and glycolytic chemical recycling of polylactide (PLA) into lactic acid (LA) and poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) into bihydroxyethyl terephthalate (BHET), respectively, aided by the protic ionic liquid 2-hydroxyethyl ammonium acetate (2-HEAA) as a homogeneous catalytic co-solvent was evaluated, and benchmarked to imidazolium-based cationic ionic liquids. Ionic liquids (IL) are appropriate catalysing co-solvents to favour the chemical recycling of polyesters, since they took part in the depolymerisation mechanisms. A factorial statistical analysis considering as factors the temperature (T), the plastic-to-ionic liquid (P/IL) and the plastic-to-solvent (P/S) mass ratios, at wide operation windows, were tested. Thermal kinetics of PET/BHET and PLA/LA were improved (i.e., the activation energy, E_a was reduced and the temperature ranges shortened and decreased) by ILs. The effect of the key process parameters was evaluated and optimized to achieve maximum PET and PLA conversions. T was the main factor for glycolysis of PET with cationic ILs and hydrolysis of PLA for aprotic ILs, while the plastic-to-solvent mass ratio was for the glycolysis of PET with protic ionic IL. The use of moderately low conversion temperatures (in contrast to metal-based ILs), minimum plastic-to-solvent ratios and reasonable plastic-to-ionic liquid ratios can represent a window of opportunity for waste-to-gate circular pathways of future polyester wastes. In terms of maximization, temperature emerged as the most significant factor, being milder compared to that applied with other catalysts, resulting in potential energy savings. From a cost-efficiency perspective, employing a high solvent proportion was deemed unnecessary, thereby reducing reagent consumption. A higher proportion of IL leads to higher conversions, which could be trace-free recovered and reused in subsequent recycling steps.

Results are presented in detail in the following publications: Badia et al. (2024), Chafer et al. (2024) and Gil-Castell et al. (2024).

Graphical abstract

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Badia JD, Ballesteros-Garrido R, Gamir-Cobacho A et al. (2024) Chemical recycling of post-consumer poly (ethylene terephthalate)(PET) driven by the protic ionic liquid 2-HEAA: Performance, kinetics and mechanism. *J Environ Chem Eng* 12:1113134

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Lignocellulosic material recovery from agro-food wastes

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Keywords: Waste; Lignocellulose; Alkali extraction; Food packaging; Up-cycling.

Abstract

Agro-food wastes or food processing by-products like peel, skin, straw, husk, cob, pomace, bagasse, mash, seed, stalk, bone and shell are emerging through harvesting, post-harvesting, processing or consumption, which still include excellent sources need to be recovered. These materials were formerly disposed by landfilling, composting, incineration or utilized as animal feedstocks at best. However, these wastes can be recycled, up-cycled, reduced, completely prevented, if possible, in order to minimize carbon footprint, optimizing energy use and create an economic value with sustainable practices. Agro-food wastes include macromolecules like proteins, pectin, mucilage and other hydrocolloids, chitosan, cellulose lipids and essential oils. In addition, they might be a good source of miscellaneous substances like bioactive compounds (e.g. phenolics, flavonoids, vitamins, bioactive peptides etc.), natural coloring agents, and serve as substrate for production of bioplastics, microbial synthesis of single cell proteins or other microbial products, nanomaterials, active carbon, biochar, biomass for biogas, biodiesel and bioethanol, and bioadsorbent of dyes. Notably, these wastes are composed of lignocellulosic materials that involve cellulose, lignin, hemicellulose, wax or lipids and other minor extractable compounds. By being abundant, cheap, renewable, low density, non-wood cellulose alternative can be exploited in further applications like using them as filler in bio-based and biodegradable food packaging films. In order to release cellulose and remove hemicellulose, lignin and impurities, lignocellulosic rich wastes are treated with alkali, acids, hydrolyzed at high temperatures, or using enzymes, or microwave or ultrasound applied. Alkali treatment with NaOH is the most common way of extraction of these lignocellulosic rich fiber, although the extraction conditions varies with concentration of alkali, temperature and period of treatment, raw material: solvent ratio, as well as employing multiple extraction steps. Following extraction, cellulosic rich fibers can be added as filler to food packaging films for improving their barrier and optical properties and mechanical strength. Overall, before utilization or up-cycling of these valuable resources, it should bear in mind that if these resources are

economically viable, always available or have seasonal variations, yield and quality (purity) are adequate or not, if there is any technological and legislation constraints, issues about public acceptance, have any potential toxic side streams, inefficient water and energy use, expenses associated with transportation of these materials and most importantly if the extraction methods are fully green methods, so cradle to cradle sustainable practice should be embraced.

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Short biography: Dr. Hulya Cakmak obtained her BSc, MSc and PhD degrees from Ege University Food Engineering Department in Izmir, Turkiye. She completed her PhD thesis entitled “Production of emulsion based edible coatings using electrospray method and their effects on the shelf-life of some fruits” in 2017. She started working as an Assist. Prof. Dr. in Hitit University Department of Food Engineering (Turkiye) in 2019 and received Assoc. Prof. Dr. title in 2023. She started her postdoctoral research in September, 2023 in University of Lleida (Spain) and continues to her studies. Dr. Cakmak is specialized in edible food coating, biodegradable food packaging and recovering lignocellulosic biomass from agro-food wastes.

Biochemical recovery of agricultural waste from grape and wine production: Sustainability in viticulture and the wine industry

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Keywords: Viticulture and winery wastes; phenolic compounds; anthocyanin; tannin; lignin.

Abstract

Viticulture and the wine industry are significant agricultural activities with substantial economic impacts on employment, regional development, and exports. Viticulture is a year-round process that generates by-products such as pruning residues, leaves, and grape stems, which can be efficiently recycled to prevent waste accumulation. The distillery industry also produces significant by-products like spent grape marc, lees cake, and vinasses. Innovative methods are needed to repurpose these by-products in line with the circular economy's 'reduce, reuse, recycle' (3R's) strategy. Pruning residues consist mainly of lignocellulosic material rich in polyphenols. These materials can be repurposed for solid biofuels, paper pulp, biochar, edible fungi cultivation, industrial materials, and bioactive compound extraction. Green pruning residues, rich in compounds like quercetin and caftaric acid, have antioxidant properties and potential as bioactive phenolic compounds (Peiretti et al. 2017). Grapevine leaves contain organic acids, phenolic acids, flavanols, tannins, and other bioactive compounds. In some Mediterranean countries, they are considered a delicacy and are also used in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries (Deliorman Orhan et al. 2009). Grape marc, the primary solid by-product of winemaking, is used for biofuel production, animal feed additives, and soil amendments (Fontana et al. 2013). Wine lees, composed of yeast, bacteria, insoluble carbohydrates, phenolic compounds, lignin, proteins, and organic acids, has potential applications as nutrient supplements, food industry additives, antioxidants, biochar for metal absorption, and polysaccharide extraction (Bustos et al. 2004). Vinasse, the wastewater from distilling low-quality wine, can be converted into useful vinasse biosolid and used for producing lactic acid, recovering tartaric acid, and biocidal effects (Liu et al. 2010). Sustainable use of grape and wine production by-products provides significant environmental and economic benefits. Utilizing these materials as raw inputs for various industries reduces waste

and fosters new economic opportunities, promoting sustainable farming and industrial practices.

Graphical abstract

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She has completed her Ph.D. at the age of 32 from Tokat Gaziosmanpasa University. She took the title of doctor with studies on viticulture. Her studies focus, in particular, on the interactions between climate change and agriculture, sustainable agriculture, ecosystem services. Her studies aim not only to provide a new perspective on waste management in the viticulture sector for environmental sustainability, but also to emphasize the potential of recycled organic materials to supply raw materials for various fields, particularly the agricultural sector. She is currently research assistant in Department of Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture, Yozgat Bozok University (YOBU).

Utilization of pyrolyzed wind turbine blade products: Emphasis on phenol-rich liquids and char as carbon black alternatives

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Keywords: Wind turbine blade; Pyrolysis; Waste-to-energy; Circular economy.

Abstract

Wind energy installations are expanding globally as part of decarbonisation efforts. While wind turbines provide green energy, they have a lifespan of around 20 years, or up to 35 years with refurbishment. By 2050, it is estimated that 43.4 million tonnes of waste wind turbine blades (WWTB) will be generated globally (Fazio et al. 2015).

WWTB is composed of a combination of fibres, a polymer matrix, a sandwich core, and various coating materials, including metals (Beauson et al. 2021). The high volatile content (approximately 50 wt.%) of WWTB indicates that the material is suitable for recycling through pyrolysis to recover resources by producing energy and alternative chemicals.

To understand the current status of WWTB pyrolysis in the literature, we collected 21 articles that specifically use WWTB as a feedstock, using keywords such as “pyrolysis”, “wind turbine”, and “wind turbine blade”. Eight articles focus on the mechanical changes in fibres after pyrolysis, while 13 articles report results from micro-scale reactors (e.g. pyrolysis in thermogravimetric analysis equipment). The remaining articles use semi-batch reactors and provide details about feedstock, process, and product characteristics.

This study aims to provide an overview of existing literature on the pyrolysis of waste wind turbine blades (WWTB) and compare these findings with the results from our experimental work. Our experiments were conducted in a continuously operated laboratory-scale pyrolysis reactor, focusing on the non-catalytic pyrolysis of WWTB. The study offers a detailed characterization of the resulting products, specifically the liquid and solid fractions. Given the high abundance of phenols (57%) in the liquid product and the significant presence of total

organic carbon (47 wt.%) and silica in the solid product, the study also explores their potential alternative uses in chemical production.

Graphical abstract

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Short biography:

Ecrin Ekici is a chemical engineer with a strong background in chemistry and holds a Master's degree in energy engineering. Her specialization lies in pyrolysis technology for the production of alternative oils from biomass, plastics, and other solid waste, including end-of-life wind turbine blades. She is currently pursuing a PhD with a focus on upgrading bio-oils to meet the co-processing requirements of (bio)refineries. Additionally, she investigates the extraction of chemicals from the aqueous phase of upgraded bio-oils to produce (bio)chemicals as a secondary research area. She also has experience with various characterization technologies used for (bio)oils and (bio)chemicals.

Phenolic-rich pyrolytic lignin: Isolation from bio-oil and application as a feedstock for low sulfur marine fuel production

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Keywords: Pyrolytic lignin; separation; Hydrodeoxygenation; Low-sulphur oils; Bio-based marine fuel.

Abstract

The marine shipping industry, mostly relying on heavy fuel oil (HFO), is one of the largest contributors to annual global sulphur (13%) (Foretich et al. 2021) and carbon emissions (3.1%) (IMO et al. 2014). To address these environmental issues, the International Maritime Organization applied regulations in 2020, mandating a sulphur content limit of 0.5% in marine fuels. To help decrease greenhouse gases, especially SO_x gases, bio-oil is a promising alternative due to its low sulphur content, which varies with the biomass source. However, upgrading bio-oil is necessary due to several drawbacks, including high oxygen content (15-70 wt.%), water content (11-40 wt.%) and low calorific value (17-35 MJ/kg) (Toscano Miranda et al. 2021). That is why hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) of bio-oil is necessary to get rid of oxygenated compounds. Bio-oil has two phases: 1) Heavy phase with around 14 wt.% of water; 2) Light phase with more than 50 wt.% of water. Pyrolytic lignin is a high molecular weight compound (e.g. 660 g/mol) in heavy phase oil can be separated by water addition to heavy phase oil. Pyrolytic lignin is more promising feedstock thanks to lower oxygen content which resembles with fossil based HFO due to carbon number range. Utilization of pyrolytic lignin to mimic HFO by HDO requires milder conditions thanks to low water and oxygenated hydrocarbons content. This study aims to provide an overview of existing literature on the HDO of pyrolytic lignin and compare these findings with the results from our experimental work. Our experiments were conducted in a high-pressure (i.e. max 300 bar) laboratory-scale batch reactor, focusing on the HDO of pyrolytic lignin at mild conditions (e.g. 250 °C and 80 bar). The study offers detailed characterization of pyrolytic lignin including suggestions of alternative usage.

Graphical abstract

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Ecrin Ekici is a chemical engineer with a strong background in chemistry and holds a Master's degree in energy engineering. Her specialization lies in pyrolysis technology for the production of alternative oils from biomass, plastics, and other solid waste, including end-of-life wind turbine blades. She is currently pursuing a PhD with a focus on upgrading bio-oils to meet the co-processing requirements of (bio)refineries. Additionally, she investigates the extraction of chemicals from the aqueous phase of upgraded bio-oils to produce (bio)chemicals as a secondary research area. She also has experience with various characterization technologies used for (bio)oils and (bio)chemicals.

MixMatters

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Keywords: Mixed agri-food waste; Industrial processes; Waste management; Bio-based products.

Abstract

The agrifood value chain produces a significant amount a mixed bio waste that contains valuable compounds like polysaccharides and polyphenol compounds [1]. However, the potential of this biowaste as a source of recycled components remains largely untapped. Approximately 75% of the generated bio waste, which accounts for around 113 million tonnes per year [2], is either disposed of in landfills or incinerated [3]. This contributes to 3% of the total greenhouse gas emissions in the EU. The effective utilisation of mixed bio waste from the agri-food sector encounters two primary obstacles. Firstly, there are technological difficulties in efficiently eliminating impurities like plastics, cardboard or metals, as these impurities have a detrimental effect on the recycling processes quality. Secondly, there are logistical obstacles in gathering raw materials that vary by season and are geographically scattered. These challenges diminish the economic advantages linked to the valorisation of bio waste.

Funded by the CBE-JU with a total budget of 5.7 million € for 4 years, MixMatters proposes an innovative system that efficiently separates and valorises three types of mixed bio-waste streams containing impurities from the agri-food industry (wholesale markets, greenhouses, food and drink industry) and obtains six high value-added outputs (powder ingredients, sugar concentrates, recombinant proteins, green fibres, bioactive compounds, plastic monomers). The separation unit is modular, multi-purpose and automated, integrating advanced robotics and AI and the integrated system is optimised via a Decision Support. The MixMatters project aims to establish three demonstration sites in Spain (two in Valencia and one in Almeria region). To focus on separating and valorizing 48 tonnes of mixed bio waste, the project goal is to reduce 21 tonnes of CO₂ emissions annually during the demonstration phase.

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2. BIC (2020) Bio-waste generation in the EU: Current capture levels and future potential ([link](#))
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Graphical abstract

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Nicolas Issaly is Doctor in Microbiology and has developed, over the past 30 years, expertise in the field of biotechnologies for the bioproduction and validation of functional ingredients for the agro-industry, cosmetics, and the pharmaceutical sector. He is the author of numerous of peer-reviewed scientific articles and patents. Nicolas Issaly has led several projects involving fermentation process, biotransformation, purification, and validation of active compounds through in vivo studies and clinical trials. European Project Leader in AINIA, a technology center based in Valencia (Spain), Nicolas Issaly is the coordinator of the MixMatters project.

Chemical recycling of plastic and textile waste

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Keywords: Plastics; Textile; Chemical recycling; Depolymerization; Thermal cracking.

Abstract

In 2021, more than 90% of world plastic production was fossil-based, and less than 10% has been collected and recycled. In Europe, figures show roughly the same trend, and the most frequent end-of-life scenario is still energy recovery by incineration (12 Mt), followed by recycling (10 Mt, mostly mechanical recycling), and landfilling (7 Mt) [1]. To tackle the air and earth pollution issues related to landfilling and incineration, much effort has been made to develop chemical recycling technologies of plastic and textile waste in combination with the existing mechanical recycling and sorting methods, in order to transform all type of plastic and textile waste into several sources of recycled materials that can be reintroduced in different levels of the value chain of plastic-based products. Depending on the nature and homogeneity of the plastic and textile waste, and on the quality of the desired products, the combination of mechanical, chemical and biological recycling methods available to date allows either the recovery of the polymers and/or its additives through dissolution-precipitation techniques (Dogu et al. 2021), or to produce monomers through depolymerisation by solvolysis of condensation polymers (Artetxe et al. 2015), pyrolysis of specific polyaddition polymers (Thiyagarajan et al. 2022), or depolymerisation by enzymes and microorganisms (Artetxe et al. 2015) or fuels and chemicals production through pyrolysis and gasification techniques (Samorì et al. 2023). In this work we present the concepts and results of various plastic, composite and textile waste recycling through the aforementioned methods at lab and pilot scale, introducing recent alternatives as the use of microwaves and mechano-chemistry for thermal cracking and depolymerisation, as well as examples of applications of the recovered materials.

Graphical abstract

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Food waste profile suitable for flexible biorefinery approach

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Keywords: Food waste; Valorization; Circular economy; Biorefinery; Flexibility.

Abstract

In the quest for sustainable development, flexible biorefineries have emerged as a pivotal innovation, offering versatile solutions for converting diverse feedstocks into valuable products. Flexible biorefinery refers to a facility capable of processing various biomass feedstocks, including food waste, to produce biofuels, biochemicals, and bioenergy through adaptable technological pathways (Smit et al. 2022). This adaptability is crucial for optimizing resource use, enhancing economic viability, and minimizing environmental impact.

This presentation delves into the potential of food waste as a primary feedstock for flexible biorefineries, addressing the pressing issue of global food waste, which accounts for approximately 1.3 billion tons annually (Rajeh et al. 2021). Food waste, rich in organic compounds, represents an untapped resource for sustainable bioproducts. By leveraging advanced technologies such as anaerobic digestion, fermentation, and hydrothermal liquefaction, we can efficiently convert food waste into bioenergy, bioplastics, and other high-value products.

Specifically, the presentation highlights the utilization of various food wastes within the flexible biorefinery framework. Case studies involving the production of biochemicals from several food wastes will be discussed. These examples illustrate the potential of food waste valorization, promoting a circular economy and reducing the environmental footprint of food production and consumption.

By embracing the flexible biorefinery approach, we can transform the challenge of food waste into an opportunity, fostering sustainable industrial practices and contributing to the global bioeconomy (Lappa et al. 2019). This presentation aims to inspire further research and collaboration in the field, emphasizing the critical role of innovative biotechnologies in addressing environmental and economic challenges.

Graphical abstract

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Critical Raw Materials: The recovery of barite (BaSO_4) from industrial effluents

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Keywords: Barite (BaSO_4); Critical Raw Materials (CRM); Resource recovery; Reuse economy; Wastewater treatment.

Abstract

Critical raw materials (CRM) are economically and strategically important for the economy, and have a high-risk associated with their supply. Currently, 30 CRM are recognized by the European Commission, including numerous metals, minerals and natural rubber [1]. Such a mineral is barite (BaSO_4) used industrially by the oil and gas industry (weighting agent in the drilling fluid), as a component of high density concrete and as additive for rubber, paint, ceramics, and glass (Staicu et al. 2020).

This presentation explores the recovery of sulfate from Flue Gas Desulfurization (FGD) effluents as barite (BaSO_4). Using equimolar BaCl_2 , complete desulfurization of an FGD effluent produced by a coal-fired power plant operating in central Poland was achieved, yielding high purity (>99%) barite. The recovered barite was characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), thermogravimetric (TGA) and scanning electron microscopy analysis (SEM), surface properties (PZC), density, and chemical stability (TCLP), and was compared with a commercial reference material. Interestingly, barite recovery also led to the precipitation of Al (86%), Cu (52%), K (69%), Mo (62%), Se (40%), Sr (91%), and U (75%), initially present in the FGD effluent. TCLP results indicate the entrapment and the stabilization of ~70% Se and ~90% Al in its structure (Staicu et al. 2020).

From a financial perspective, BaCl_2 (the input reagent) is 1.3-2.1 times more expensive than BaSO_4 (the output). However, the price of the reagents varies based on assay (%). No reliable sources were found for industrial-grade reagents in large quantities (e.g. metric ton) that would make the process attractive from a financial point of view. Other limitations of these process are related to formation of solid products, the secondary pollution (e.g. Cl^- , Ba^{2+} and electrical conductivity) entailing additional treatment system(s) downstream and the potential legal

limitations for reusing a material resulted from waste. Nevertheless, the treatment of industrial effluents based on BaSO_4 precipitation could be an incentive due to the removal of toxic metals present in these matrices and their stabilization in such an insoluble mineral (Staicu et al. 2017; Staicu et al. 2022).

Graphical abstract (source: Staicu et al. 2020)

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Short biography:

I am researcher at Institute of Microbiology, Faculty of Biology, University of Warsaw (Poland), working on microbial biotechnology and geomicrobiology. I am particularly interested in the interaction of bacteria with metals (biomineralization, detoxification and respiration processes) and in the production of (bio)minerals having high-industrial value (e.g. Se^0 , PbS , BaSO_4). Another research direction we are pursuing is the bioremediation of metal-laden industrial effluents such as those generated by the mining industry and the chemical recovery of barite (BaSO_4), a Critical Raw Material (CRM) in the European Union.

Resource recovery from food wastes

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Keywords: Food wastes; Fungi; Anaerobic bacteria; Resource recovery; Biorefinery.

Abstract

This presentation delves into the transformative potential of resource recovery from food wastes, underscoring the vision that waste is a valuable resource. The food wastes have various technical challenges such as the recalcitrance of lignocellulosic materials, the presence of toxic substances, and the complexities arising from mixed waste streams. In addition, the wastes have economic hurdles like high transportation and processing costs, regulatory challenges surrounding the use of recovered products as food and feed, and social challenges related to societal mindsets.

Various pretreatment methods are explored - ranging from physical techniques like milling and irradiation to chemical processes including steam explosion and the use of acids and oxidizing agents - to enhance material accessibility for enzymatic hydrolysis and to remove contaminants. Biological pretreatments utilizing white-rot fungi and *Bacillus pumilus* are also highlighted for their efficacy in breaking down complex waste components such as lignin or keratins.

The concept of biorefineries is further explored, where pretreated waste materials can be converted into valuable products such as biogas, ethanol, biopolymers, and biocomposites. It is an important aspects to break down the total cost per unit of the products. The presentation showcases examples like fungal biomass as fish feed and bioplastics derived from anaerobic digestion byproducts. Another such examples is the potential of integrating biorefineries within existing industrial setups, particularly in first-generation ethanol plants, so the residuals of such process can be consumed of the fungi to produce fungal biomass and more ethanol. Another example is the integration of membrane systems to facilitate the recovery of a wide range of materials including volatile fatty acids (VFAs) and energy, transforming biogas plants into multifunctional biorefineries. The innovative use of VFAs as carbon sources in wastewater treatment, production of bioplastics or using as animal feed are also examined.

Therefore, a shift in perception and policy to leverage the full potential of food waste recovery is possible. Emphasizing learning from nature and utilizing microorganisms to aid in waste transformation, it posits that with the right technologies and societal mindset shifts, food waste can significantly contribute to sustainability, resource efficiency, and the reduction of hunger.

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Mohammad J. Taherzadeh is professor in Bioprocess technology since 2004 at Swedish Centre for Resource Recovery, University of Borås in Sweden. Prof. Taherzadeh has PhD in Bioscience, and MSc and BSc in Chemical Engineering. He is developing bioprocesses to convert wastes and residuals to value added products with focus on pretreatment and fermentation using anaerobic bacteria and filamentous fungi. He has more than 500 publications, and with strong collaboration with industries he developed several bioprocesses in industrial scales.

Production of chemical building blocks for the plastic industry from organic waste

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Keywords: Bioplastics; Organic waste; Fermentation; Lactic acid; Building blocks.

Abstract

Bioplastics are a whole family of materials with different properties and applications. A plastic material can be defined as a bioplastic if it is either bio-based, biodegradable, or both at the same time. Biobased plastics are fully or partially made from biological resources. Organic waste, encompassing agricultural residues, food scraps, and municipal solid waste, presents a rich source of carbon compounds, mostly in the form of lignocellulosic biomass, and it constitutes an interesting secondary resource for the production of bioplastics. Fermentation processes carried out by microorganisms allow the conversion of these waste streams into high-value chemical, such as lactic acid, which serve as precursors for bioplastics. However, the lignocellulosic biomass requires pretreatments to free the fermentable sugars contained within cellulose and hemicellulose. Different possibilities for pretreatment include alkali, acid, steam explosion, enzymatic pretreatments, or a combination of these. Designing an efficient pretreatment is key in ensuring a good sugar yield for the fermentation process. Microbial agents can be selected based on the target product and recent advancements in genetic engineering of microorganisms can help to enhance yield and process efficiency. The feasibility of implementing these technologies on an industrial scale, including the challenges of feedstock variability and process optimization, need to be addressed when designing these processes. AIMPLAS has worked with organic waste from different origins and, taking advantage of the rich microbial diversity, we have been able to produce high-added value products such as lactic acid for the production of the bioplastic PLA; 2,3-butanediol, a precursor to synthetic rubber; or succinic acid and 1,4-butanediol, the precursor molecules to produce PBS.

Graphical abstract

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Short biography: Researcher in the Biotechnology unit at AIMPLAS. I received my PhD from the University of Valencia where I worked in industrial microbiology of non-conventional yeasts at the Institute of Integrative Systems Biology. Afterwards, I joined the Valencian Institute of Microbiology to expand my expertise in the microbiology field. Currently, I am working at AIMPLAS, researching fermentation processes to obtain bioplastics and new biotechnology-based methods to recycle electrical and electronic waste and minimize the loss of natural resources.

Recovery of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) from different waste streams

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Keywords: Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs); Respirometric assessment; Volatile fatty acids (VFAs); Wheat processing wastewaters; Mixed microbial culture (MMC).

Abstract

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biologically-produced thermoplastics derived from various feedstocks. Their bio-based and biodegradable nature makes them an attractive renewable alternative to conventional petroleum-based plastics (Naser et al. 2021). Waste streams that have high organic carbon content are a promising source for PHA production. Most of the production cost of PHAs is related to the carbon source and pure culture fermentation (Yin et al. 2020). Mixed microbial consortia (MMC) can eliminate contamination risks and sterilization requirements, and thus provides low-cost PHA production (Liao et al. 2018; Carvalho et al. 2022). Wheat processing industrial wastewaters are characterized by their high COD content and, therefore, anaerobic treatment is regarded as the most feasible and appropriate treatment process for such wastewaters. Wheat processing industry wastewater is examined to investigate the potential of PHA production from VFAs generated during the anaerobic treatment process. The extent of PHA production was assessed at various stages of acidogenic fermentation of wheat processing wastewaters, in order to optimize both the amount and the polymer composition of PHAs produced from VFAs. The respirometric assessment results showed that fermented wheat processing wastewaters could be efficiently used and optimized for the production of PHAs in addition to the high amount of biogas generation through methanation. The textile finishing industry is a highly water-intensive sector, where deeper investigation into recovery options is needed due to the significant organic carbon content in specific streams. Softening process wastewaters of textile finishing operations is directly used as feed source due to its VFA content. Despite the presence of dyes and various chemicals in the textile wastewater composition, MMC was able to grow without inhibition and store PHA. In the experimental studies on wheat processing and textile finishing effluents, maximum PHA storage was determined by accumulation tests. Moreover, the extraction of

PHA (PHB, PHV and PH2MV) was performed using sodium hydroxide (NaOH), sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) and waste NaOH from textile bleaching process in the context of reuse strategy. Different biomass pre-treatment methods (fresh, dried and lyophilized) were tested to determine optimal conditions for pre-processing steps.

Graphical abstract

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I am a PhD student and a faculty member at Istanbul Technical University. I have 7 years of experience as a process engineer at wastewater treatment plants in Istanbul. Currently, I am researching on bioplastic production from various industrial waste streams.

Valorization of liquid side streams from softwood bark carbonization

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Keywords: Slow pyrolysis; Bark; Condensable gases; Valorization; Anti-fungal.

Abstract

Slow pyrolysis represents a promising way to valorize forest industry by-products by thermal conversion into added-value products, specifically biochar. Besides biochar, aqueous side streams are generated containing the condensed gas fraction. This latter often makes a significant amount of low-added value by-product referred to as pyrolysis liquid. Prior literature (Black et al. 2016; Boer et al. 2020; Marrot et al. 2022) revealed the occurrence of active compounds with interesting properties (e.g., antioxidant, antibacterial, etc.) in the pyrolysis liquid of variable feedstocks. The recovery and valorization of such compounds can be promising to enhance the sustainability and profitability of the slow pyrolysis process. This study aimed to characterize pyrolysis liquid from softwood bark and to evaluate its potential anti-fungal activity against food-decaying fungi. The pyrolysis of bark biomass was conducted in a tube furnace for 30 min at 800 °C under a nitrogen atmosphere. Different pyrolysis liquid fractions were collected at variable temperature ranges (F1: 25-260 °C, F2: 260-512 °C, F3: 512-800 °C, and F4: 800-25 °C). The total phenolic content, functional groups, and molecular composition of the samples were assessed. The anti-fungal activity against food-decaying fungi, specifically *Cladosporium* sp. and *Aspergillus versicolor*, was evaluated using the disk diffusion test. The liquid fraction F2 collected at a temperature range between 260-512 °C had the highest total phenolic content among all other samples. This result was attributed to the high rate of biomass degradation at this range of temperature. The functional group analysis of the same sample (F2) revealed the occurrence of variable groups such as hydroxyl, carboxylic acid, carbonyl, and aromatics. The liquid chromatography analysis detected the presence of furan derivatives, specifically 5-hydroxymethylfurfural, furfural, and 5-methylfurfural, in sample F2. However, other samples were less concentrated. After incubation of the fungi in the presence of F2, an inhibition zone was observed informing about the potential anti-fungal activity of the compounds contained in the collected pyrolysis liquid.

Graphical abstract

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Short biography: Mariem Zouari is a researcher at InnoRenew CoE (Slovenia). She earned her bachelor's degree in applied biotechnology from the Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Sfax (Tunisia) and a professional master's degree in food sciences and technologies at the same institution. At Szent Istvan University (Hungary), she finished an engineering master's program in food biotechnology, where she worked on biodegradable composites as a final project. In 2024, she earned her PhD from the University of Primorska (Slovenia). Her research activities focus on thermal conversion, biocarbon, material composites, and functional coatings for air purification.

Conclusions & Perspectives

The **FULLRECO4US - Cost Action 20133** “Cross Border Transfer and Development of Sustainable Resource Recovery Strategies Towards Zero Waste” workshop, “**Matching diverse feedstocks for biochemical recovery: Impact of their quality**”, was held in Valencia (Spain), 10-11 July 2024. The workshop featured 14 oral presentations and a guided tour at AIMPLAS facilities (Valencia). The oral presentations ranged from biochemical resource recovery using food/organic/agricultural waste materials to the recycling of plastic wastes and critical raw materials (CRM). This event represented a unique opportunity for experts, researchers, and practitioners working in academia and industry from across Europe and beyond to share insights, brainstorm valuable ideas, and foster collaborations in the framework of sustainable resource recovery. An important pillar of the workshop was the thorough understanding and characterization of the diverse feedstocks and the need to recycle them to generate resources with higher added value. This not only reduces the waste burden to the environment, but it also recovers resources, thus limiting the pressure on the primary sources and also contributing to a better implementation of the circular economy.

The participants stressed the need for better connectivity between academia and industry and for organizing more events bringing together scientists from both sides of the fence. Furthermore, future networking opportunities such as this workshop will bring valuable insights and perspectives for an efficient resource recovery. Future events should include case studies and original results based on real feedstocks (the so-called “waste” streams). This may help to accelerate the transition to a zero waste paradigm shift and to achieving the sustainable development goals. Partnerships and collaborations to initiate, develop, and implement projects are essential to share knowledge and to bring complementary expertise from all participants. The complexity of implementing a global resource recovery strategy should be addressed by a multidisciplinary approach featuring researchers from various research disciplines.

We believe that this workshop will stimulate future joint research projects, practical solutions, and a generous scientific output that may be of interest to society as a whole. It is our hope that this work can inspire and promote new research that could be included in a European call for proposals, while promoting the active participation of industry, therefore any entity interested in collaborating with us in this objective will be welcome.

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Group photo of the workshop participants (July 11, 2024; Valencia, Spain)

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